

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Rahimova Dilfuza

CHET TILLARINI AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VOSITASIDA

SAMARALI O'RGANISH

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ